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Basic survey on Malware Analysis, Tools and Techniques

Dolly Uppal¹, Vishakha Mehra¹ and Vinod Verma², ¹Rajasthan Technical University, India and ²Govt. Engineering College, India

Abstract

The term malware stands for malicious software. It is a program installed on a system without the knowledge of owner of the system. It is basically installed by the third party with the intention to steal some private data from the system or simply just to play pranks. This in turn threatens the computer's security, wherein computer are used by one's in day-to-day life as to deal with various necessities like education, communication, hospitals, banking, entertainment etc. Different traditional techniques are used to detect and defend these malwares like Antivirus Scanner (AVS), firewalls, etc. But today malware writers are one step forward towards then Malware detectors. Day-by-day they write new malwares, which become a great challenge for malware detectors. This paper focuses on basis study of malwares and various detection techniques which can be used to detect malwares.

Keywords

Malware, obfuscation, normalization, Deobfuscation, oligomorphic etc.

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Authors

Dolly Uppal

Scholar of Masters of Technology from Rajasthan Technical University, Kota, Rajasthan, India. Passed out B.Tech. From Rajasthan Technical University, Kota, Rajasthan, India in 2012. Research area: Malware Analysis

Vishakha Mehra

Scholar of Masters of Technology from Rajasthan Technical University, Kota, Rajasthan, India. Passed out B.Tech. From Rajasthan Technical University, Kota, Rajasthan, India in 2011. Research are a: Malware Analysis

